

COVID-19 Bibliometrics 21th – 27th December 2020

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A. Medicine and Health

December 23, 2020 (EClinMed)

Safety and immunogenicity of INO-4800 DNA vaccine against SARS-CoV2: A preliminary report of an open-label, Phase 1 clinical trial.

Pablo Tebas, ShuPing Yang, Jean D. Boyer et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100689>

INO-4800 is a DNA vaccine targeting the full length spike antigen of SARS-CoV-2. Of the 38 human subjects who received both doses of the vaccine, immunogenicity was seen in 100% of them by eliciting either or both humoral or cellular immune responses. No serious adverse events were reported. INO-4800 demonstrated safety and tolerability.

December 23, 2020 (JAMA Netw. Open)

Assessment of Air Contamination by SARS-CoV-2 in Hospital Settings

Gabriel Birgand, Nathan Peiffer-Smadja, Sandra Fournier et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.33232>

This systematic review distills the current evidence on air contamination with severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) in hospital settings and assesses the factors associated with contamination, including viral load and particle size.

December 22, 2020 (NEJM)

A Neutralizing Monoclonal Antibody for Hospitalized Patients with Covid-19

ACTIV-3/TICO LY-CoV555 Study Group

<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa2033130>

In this trial involving 314 hospitalized COVID-19 patients who were receiving remdesivir, those who received the monoclonal antibody LY-CoV555 did not have a better pulmonary function at day 5 than those who received placebo. The trial was stopped for futility.

December 18, 2020 (Science)

An ultrapotent synthetic nanobody neutralizes SARS-CoV-2 by stabilizing inactive Spike

Michael Schoof, Bryan Faust, Reuben A. Saunders et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe3255>

Monoclonal antibodies that bind to the spike protein of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) show therapeutic promise

but must be produced in mammalian cells and need to be delivered intravenously. By contrast, single-domain antibodies called nanobodies can be produced in bacteria or yeast, and their stability may enable aerosol delivery. Schoof *et al.* screened a yeast surface display of synthetic nanobodies and identified highly potent nanobodies that lock the spike protein in an inactive conformation.

[December 14, 2020 \(JAMA Netw. Open\)](#)

Household Transmission of SARS-CoV2: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis

Madewell ZJ, Yang Y, Longini IM, Halloran ME, Dean NE.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.31756>

This systematic review and meta-analysis examines the evidence for household transmission of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), disaggregated by several covariates, and compares it with other coronaviruses

[December 4, 2020 \(Science\)](#)

Comparative host-coronavirus protein interaction networks reveal pan-viral disease mechanisms

David E. Gordon, Joseph Hiatt, Mehdi Bouhaddou *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe9403>

Shedding light on the host factors taken over by the viruses, Gordon *et al.* mapped the interactions between viral and human proteins for SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV-1, and MERS-CoV. They analyzed the localization of viral proteins in human cells and used genetic screening to identify host factors that either enhance or inhibit viral infection.

[December 4, 2020 \(Science\)](#)

De novo design of potent and resilient hACE2 decoys to neutralize SARS-CoV-2

Thomas W. Linsky, Renan Vergara, Nuria Codina *et al.*

<https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abe0075>

Linsky *et al.* describe a de novo design strategy that allowed them to engineer decoy proteins that bind to the spike protein by replicating the hACE2 interface. CTC-445 was found to be the best decoy as it bound with low nanomolar affinity. Additionally, the selection of viral mutants that could cause a decrease in binding is unlikely because this would affect binding to hACE2. A bivalent version of CTC-445 bound even more tightly, neutralized SARS-CoV2 infection of cells and protected hamsters from a SARS-CoV2 challenge.

B. Science and Engineering

January 12, 2021 (Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences)

Structure of SARS-CoV-2 ORF8, a rapidly evolving immune evasion protein
Thomas G. Flower, Cosmo Z. Buffalo, Richard M. Hooy et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2021785118>

This highly technical paper reports on the structure of the ORF8 which is a rapidly evolving accessory protein that has been proposed to interfere with immune responses. The structure reveals a ~60-residue core similar to SARS-CoV-2 ORF7a, with the addition of two dimerization interfaces unique to SARS-CoV-2 ORF8. The presence of these interfaces shows how SARS-CoV-2 ORF8 can form unique large-scale assemblies not possible for SARS-CoV, potentially mediating unique immune suppression and evasion activities.

January 4, 2021 (Communications Biology)

Fast automated detection of COVID-19 from medical images using convolutional neural networks

Shuang Liang, Huixiang Lui, Yu Gu et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-020-01535-7>

The researchers use pseudo-colouring methods and a platform for annotating X-ray and computed tomography images to train the convolutional neural network, which achieves a performance similar to that of experts and provides high scores for multiple statistical indices (F1 scores > 96.72% and specificity >99.33%). Heatmaps are used to visualize the salient features extracted by the neural network. The proposed method represents a potential computer-aided diagnosis method for COVID-19 in clinical practice.

December 31, 2020 (International Journal of Infectious Diseases)

Comparing COVID-19 vaccine allocation strategies in India: A mathematical modelling study

Brody H. Foy, Brian Wahl, Kayur Mehta et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2020.12.075>

The authors used an age-structured, expanded SEIR model with social contact matrices to assess age-specific vaccine allocation strategies in India. They used state-specific age structures and disease transmission coefficients estimated from confirmed incident cases of COVID-19 between 1 July and 31 August 2020. Simulations were used to investigate the relative reduction in mortality and morbidity of vaccine allocation strategies based on prioritizing different age groups. They showed that prioritizing COVID-19 vaccine allocation for older populations (i.e., >60 years) led to the greatest relative reduction in deaths, regardless of vaccine efficacy, control measures, rollout speed, or immunity dynamics. Their findings support global recommendations to prioritize vaccine allocation for older age groups.

December 11, 2020 (Results in Physics)

Modeling and prediction of COVID-19 spread in the Philippines by October 13, 2020, by using the VARMAX time series method with preventive measures

Parikshit Gautam Jamdade & Shrinivas Gautamrao Jamdade.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2020.103694>

The authors examined the characteristics of COVID-19 affected populations based on the data provided by WHO from December 31, 2019, to September 13, 2020. In this paper, forecasts, and analysis of the COVID-19 cases, deaths, cases per million, and deaths per million were presented for 30 days ahead. The projection results are compared with the actual data values and simulated results from the VARMAX time series method. They suggested Philippines governments must rapidly mobilize and make good policy decisions to mitigate the spread.

C. Social Sciences, Humanities and Public Policies

January 1, 2021 (Social Sciences & Humanities Open)

The COVID-19 Pandemic: A Focusing Event to Promote Community Midwifery Policies in the United States

Adelle Dora Montebianco

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100104>

The pandemic stress has changed prenatal, labour, delivery, and postpartum care in the U.S., motivating many pregnant people to seek maternal health care with community midwives. This work theorizes that the COVID-19-related disrupted health care system and the increased visibility of community midwives may create a “focusing event,” which may enable midwives and their advocates to impact on policy.

December 21, 2020 (Social Science & Humanities Open)

When the gigs are gone: Valuing arts, culture and media in the COVID-19 pandemic

M. Sharon Jeannotte

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2020.100097>

This article proposes a four-part conceptual framework that uses economic, social, creative, and sustainability lenses to examine the immediate impact of the pandemic on creators, curators and the media. They review a sample of policy and creative responses to these challenges and then discusses the implications for how governments and citizens benefit from the creative initiatives.

December 17, 2020 (Journal of Social Work)

Social work involvement in the COVID-19 response in China: Interdisciplinary remote networking

Zhihong Yu, Qiqi Chen, Guanghuai Zheng et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1468017320980657>

This article introduces the innovative interdisciplinary remote networking framework which both provides a guide for medical and community social workers' involvement during the pandemic. This framework also provides an effective model for setting up a targeted and sustained service system that links social workers with psychological and medical resources. The frontline experiences of social work interventions in China may serve as an example for other countries. This framework presents implications for future practice development in both disaster social work and public health social work.

December 5, 2020 (Forensic Science International)

Violence against women in the Covid-19 pandemic: A review of the literature and a call for shared strategies to tackle health and social emergencies

A. Viero, G. Barbara, M. Montisci et al.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forsciint.2020.110650>

Viero et al conducted a critical review about the relationship between violence against women (VAW) and the current pandemic. The review confirmed that the “stay at home” policies to contrast the pandemic have increased the problem of VAW. However, rigorous studies estimating the relationship between VAW and pandemic are scarce, most published data are derived from social media, internet, anecdotal evidence and helplines reports. Creative solutions are needed to solve the VAW problems.